

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: UNITED STATES

The Conference of the Lakes: Art and science come together to highlight threats to lakes around the world.

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“What are the sciences? Only categories for thinking. Sciences can be taught separately, but they can't be used separately, either for seeing land or doing anything with it. What is art? Only the drama of the land's working.”

Aldo Leopold, North American Wildlife Conference 1942

“If you've seen one lake, you've seen one lake.”

A phrase heard often at a Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network (GLEON) meeting

Art is a valuable tool to connect science to the broader public. Science-art collaborations can effectively transmit concepts and reshape misconceptions (Arce-Nazario, 2016). Art acts as a framework for visual and social experiences, which can create empathy towards the natural environment and generate appreciation (Marks *et al.*, 2016). These emotional and aesthetic connections can make people more willing to invest in conserving what they appreciate and value (Curtis, 2009). In many ways, science and art are not that different from each other. Science itself is a creative process, and historically co-production in science and art was more common (*e.g.*, Leonardo da Vinci; Solina, 2022). Recent studies have found similarities in the thought processes and habitats used in art and science (Root-Bernstein *et al.*, 2019; Scheffer *et al.*, 2017), as well as correlations between art practices and scientific achievement (Root-Bernstein *et al.*, 2019).

Here we describe a science-art collaboration that highlights the issues lakes face across the world, through creating ‘portraits’ of each lake. Catherine O'Reilly and Alice Hargraves worked together to create artwork using datasets from various lakes, including at least one from each continent (cover photo, Fig.1). Many of these datasets were gathered from members of Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network (GLEON) after Hargrave and O'Reilly attended the 2019 annual meeting. Once lakes and datasets were selected, Hargrave and O'Reilly talked to researchers who studied those lakes to learn more about the broader context. In addition, Hargrave

did a 1-month residency at Flathead Lake Biological Station, which allowed her to work with aquatic scientists, go sampling on the lake, and have time to immerse herself in creating the artwork. Funding for this project came from The Andy Warhol Foundation for the Visual Arts through a grant written by Kendra Paitz, Director and Chief Curator at University Galleries of Illinois State University.

Each ‘lake portrait’ is based on the patterns of the scientific data from that lake. The artwork incorporates published or unpublished data that describes the environmental issue for that lake. Hargrave often used the original colors from the scientific figure, as in her world of photography she wanted to keep an element of truth in the work despite the fact that colors in the data are simply random unlike the dictum in art that she follows of “form follows function” — that there should be a reason for every color choice in the art, even if it is a due to subjective emotional expression. Each “lake portrait” is a unique pattern created with diverse source material—the data, vintage photos associated with the lake, and photos Hargrave was able to make, often using colors of the water itself, including underwater photography. Printed on semi-transparent fabric, a lake portrait is 3 meters tall and 1.5 m wide, and is typically hung with other lake portraits in a multi-layered installation, echoing the idea of a conference of interconnected waters. Initially, 20 lakes were done, representing each of the seven continents (Table 1), and we continue to expand to other lakes. These lakes also represent a range of climate change influences. Some lakes are warming, some lakes are drying up, and some lakes are being born as glaciers melt. Other lakes are experiencing changes in their chemistry, species compositions, and food web dynamics.

The collection of pieces is titled *The Conference of the Lakes*, in reference to Farid ud-Din Attar's 12th-century poem, *The Conference of the Birds*. This poem alludes to the challenging journey taken to reach enlightenment, along with the excuses that hinder progress - in much the same way humanity has been making excuses for not tackling the climate crises. The poem also underscores ideas of individuality that are reflected in each lake's individual portrait. Incorporated into the story is the idea that people do have the ability to evolve, and that the journey can be one of success if surmounted as a group (*e.g.*, a conference) rather than by individuals with selfish, short-sighted goals. The title is also an allusion to the gathering of scientists at their own conferences.

The collection and individual lake portraits have been shown at multiple exhibitions. The premiere exhibition opened in March 2021 at the University Galleries, Illinois State University, as part of *Alice Hargrave: The Canary in the Lake* (Figs. 2, 3). The exhibition ran for three months and also included real-time virtual tours that created the 3-dimensional experience of walking among the lakes. These virtual tours allowed people from around the USA and other countries to view the exhibition. Faculty from science and non-science courses integrated the exhibition into their curriculum. The collaborators participated virtually in class visits and tours, which allowed Hargrave to describe her process and O'Reilly to explain the environmental impacts. [This exhibition is available online](#) as part of the 2021 archives. The online material includes photos and video as well as extensive information that describes each lake portrait in more detail, including the sources of the data and citations for scientific papers about each lake. Over the last year, pieces have also been shown in five other galleries and cultural centers in Virginia, Illinois, Montana, and New York.

Fig. 1 A partial view of the installation *The Conference of the Lakes after Farid Attar*, in University Galleries at Illinois State University, USA, 2021. Each lake ‘portrait’ is printed on a large fabric piece that hangs from the ceiling, with 11 portraits visible here. The colors on the lake portraits are often taken from photos of the lakes, and the patterns are taken from datasets, in some cases with other images related to the lake being incorporated into the piece as well. Altogether, the portraits highlight the diversity of lakes, how unique each lake is, and the range of environmental issues faced by lakes around the world. Photo by M. Hassel, University Galleries.

Fig. 2 In the background between two hanging lake portraits is another installation by Alice Hargrave titled Herbarium, lake algae, macrophytes, 2020-2021. This work is 29 pigment prints photographed from the collection of the Flathead Lake Biological Station in Montana, USA.

Fig. 3 A visitor is seen through a lake portrait, highlighting their transparent nature. The ability to wander among the hanging portraits reflects the three-dimensional nature of lakes themselves. Photo by M. Hassel, University Galleries.

What do Hargrave and O'Reilly hope the public gains from viewing this artwork? One of the goals for this exhibition was to help audiences recognize how unique each lake is, by offering an experiential engagement that visualizes what is often invisible. Ultimately, the idea was to create a space that helps people move beyond the 2-dimensional surface of a lake, to appreciate the complexity that exists below the surface and within a landscape and historical context. One visitor instantly started twirling and dancing through the hanging fabrics, and another instinctively reached out to touch them (they are touchable!). Although each lake portrait reflects different environmental stressors and impacts, this more detailed information requires reading the titles and/or other contextual information offered on wall text and online. Even if visitors walk out only reflecting on the idea that lakes are unique and are being affected by change, that's a successful step in helping people appreciate their world and hopefully be more willing to enact change.

References

- Arce-Navario J. 2016. Translating land use science to a museum exhibit. *Journal of Land Use Science* 11: 417-428.
- Curtis DJ. 2009. Creating inspiration: The role of the arts in creating empathy for ecological restoration *Ecological Management and Restoration* 10: 174-184.
- Marks M, Chandler L, Baldwin C. 2016. Environmental art as an innovative medium for environmental education in Biosphere Reserves. *Environmental Education Research* 7: 1-15.
- Root-Bernstein R, Van Dyke M, Persuki A, Root-Bernstein M. 2019. Correlation between tools for thinking; arts, crafts, and design avocations; and scientific achievement among STEM professionals. *PNAS* 116: 1910-1917.
- Scheffer M, Baas M, Bjordam TK. 2017. Teaching originality? Common habits behind creative production in science and arts. *Ecology and Society* 22: 29.
- Solina F. 2022. Creativity in Science and Art. In: Brito SM, Thomaz JPCF. (Eds.). *Creativity*. IntechOpen, London.

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Table 1. List of existing lake portraits - *The Conference of the Lakes, after Farid Attar* - solvent prints on fabric of lake portraits
3 m x 1.5 m ea. 2020 - 2021

Panel	Lake	Country	Issue
1	Lake Baikal	Russia	warming
2	Lake Tanganyika	Tanzania	warming, fish loss
3	Lake Vanda	Antarctica	growing lake, ice melt
4	Lake Hillier	Australia	genome of <i>S. ruber</i> , pink lake
5	Lake Tovel	Italy	warming
6	Lake Zigadenus	Canada	decreasing turbidity "Losing Blue"
7	The Loch & Sky Pond	Colorado, USA	atmospheric nitrogen deposition
8	Lake Tahoe	USA	decreasing clarity
9	Lake Otsego	New York, USA	warming, invasive species
10	Lake Tovel	Italy	magenta algal bloom loss
11	Northern Wisconsin Lakes	USA	mercury
12	Lake Superior	USA	ice loss
13	Lake Abiyata	Ethiopia	shrinking lake, habitat loss
14	Lakes Mendota, Menona, and Wingra	Wisconsin, USA	rising salinity
15	Lake Milford	Kansas, USA	toxic algal blooms
16	Lake Thingvallavatn	Iceland	ice loss, finger rafting
17	Lake Escanaba, Wisconsin	USA	phenological whiplash
18	Lake Blavatn	Iceland	new lake, glacier extinction
19	El Morado Proglacial Lake	Chile	new lake before green
20	Flathead Lake	Montana, USA	invasive species and mercury in the food chain